

Evaluation of Potentially Inappropriate Medications (PIMs) in Outpatient Geriatric Patients at RSKO Jakarta

Arbella Veronica^{1*}, Rizky Farmasita², Ahda Sabila³, Alhara Yuwanda⁴, Nopratilova⁵, Anugerah Budi⁶

^{1,2,3,4,5,6}Departement of Pharmacy, Jakarta Global University, Depok, Indonesia.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: The global incidence of Potentially Inappropriate Medication Use (PIM) in elderly patients ranges from 6% to 41%. Research indicates that some medications are not recommended for elderly patients due to their side effects outweighing clinical benefits. The American Geriatrics Society developed the Beers Criteria as guidelines in clinical practice and research to identify PIM and guide medication management in elderly patients. This study aims to assess the prevalence of inappropriate medication prescriptions in elderly outpatients at RSKO Jakarta using the Beers Criteria. Additionally, the study analyzes the relationship between polypharmacy and comorbidities with PIM occurrence.

Methods: The sample consists of elderly patients from general and internal medicine clinics at RSKO Jakarta from January to August 2023. This non-experimental study employs a descriptive approach, collecting retrospective data from 110 prescriptions. The data is analyzed univariately and bivariately using the chi-square test to determine the relationships between polypharmacy, comorbidities, and the occurrence of PIM.

Results: The study found that 53.64% of prescriptions for elderly patients at RSKO Jakarta were identified as PIMs, with 11.54% categorized under "avoid" and 88.46% under "use with caution." The most commonly prescribed PIMs were glimepiride (16.25%), gabapentin (15%), and omeprazole (13.75%). The findings indicate a significant relationship between polypharmacy ($p=0.000$) and comorbidities ($p=0.000$) with PIM occurrence.

Conclusion: These results highlight the need for further evaluation of medication prescribing patterns for elderly patients at RSKO Jakarta. The significant association between polypharmacy and comorbidities with PIM occurrence underscores the importance of careful medication management in this population, using guidelines such as the Beers Criteria to minimize the risks of inappropriate medication use.

KEYWORDS: PIMs; Beers Criteria; Geriatri

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
29 August 2024

Available on:
<http://ijpbms.com>

I. INTRODUCTION

The incidence of PIMs in geriatrics is widespread worldwide, with an estimated prevalence ranging from 6% to 41%¹. Research by Wulansari et al (2023)² showed that 63.1% of geriatric patients experienced PIMs based on the Beers Criteria 2019, while 36.9% did not. Another study by³ found that out of 115 geriatric patients, 56 (48.70%) had potential inappropriate medication use (PIMs).

Potentially Inappropriate Medications (PIMs) are defined as drugs that should be avoided because their risk of adverse effects outweighs their clinical benefits, especially

when safer or more effective alternative therapies are available for the same condition⁴. PIMs can increase the risk of falls in the elderly, particularly those with side effects on the nervous system or blood pressure, which can lead to serious injuries. Additionally, PIMs with anticholinergic effects or side effects on the central nervous system can cause cognitive issues, such as confusion and memory impairment, in older adults⁵.

In 2019, the American Geriatrics Society (AGS) published the "Beers Criteria for Potentially Inappropriate Medication Use in Older Adults," intended as a prescribing

Evaluation of Potentially Inappropriate Medications (PIMs) in Outpatient Geriatric Patients at RSKO Jakarta

guide for geriatric patients. This guideline aims to avoid riskier or more harmful side effects, thereby reducing the incidence of PIMs. Thus, there is a relationship between the Beers Criteria and PIMs in geriatric patients. The Beers Criteria provide clinical guidance to help identify medications with high potential risks or side effects in the geriatric population, which can consequently be considered PIMs in this context.

Factors influencing the occurrence of PIM prescriptions include comorbidities and polypharmacy status. According to Kharunisa dkk (2023)⁶ research, the number of comorbidities has a significant relationship with the incidence of PIMs, with a Sig value of 0.047. This indicates a correlation between the occurrence of potentially inappropriate medication use and the number of accompanying diseases. Comorbidities are medical conditions in which an individual suffers from two or more different diseases or conditions simultaneously⁷. Geriatric patients are prone to adverse drug reactions due to high comorbidity and the aging process, which disrupts drug metabolism⁸

Another influencing factor is polypharmacy status. A study in Canada found that 29.9% of geriatric patients use five or more medications simultaneously⁴. Polypharmacy is the use of multiple types of medications by one individual simultaneously or sequentially to treat one or more diseases. The use of many medications often increases the risk of side effects, which can trigger the likelihood of PIM prescriptions and adverse drug interactions that harm patient health⁹. The reason for conducting this study at RSKO Jakarta is the lack of research on general patients, particularly geriatrics, at RSKO Jakarta, which makes this an important area of focus. This study

aims to evaluate potentially inappropriate medications (PIMs) among geriatric outpatients and explore factors associated with the increased risk of PIM use in this population. The study uses a retrospective design, with data collected from the medical records at RSKO Jakarta.

II. METHODS

This study is an analytical observational study. The data used consists of all drug prescriptions from geriatric outpatient clinics and internal medicine departments that meet the inclusion and exclusion criteria during the period from January 2023 to August 2023. Data collection was conducted retrospectively. Prior to identifying PIMs occurrences, the primary diseases of the patients were grouped according to the ICD X guidelines, and the level of comorbidities was categorized based on the Charlson Comorbidity Index. Identification of PIM occurrences was carried out using the Beers Criteria 2019 guidelines by categorizing medications into "avoid" and "use with caution" categories. Data were obtained from prescription reports at the pharmacy installation and tracing patient medical records. Sampling was done using total sampling technique.

The data will be analyzed using statistical analysis. Univariate data analysis was performed to observe the prevalence of PIMs in geriatric outpatient patients. Bivariate analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between PIM occurrences with comorbid diseases and PIM occurrences with polypharmacy status using nonparametric chi-square tests. Descriptive data were managed in Microsoft Excel, and statistical data were analyzed using SPSS Ver. 24.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Patient Demographic Profile

Table 1. Demographics of geriatric outpatients at the Drug Dependency Hospital for the period of January-August 2023

Criteria	Number of Patients (n=110)	Percentag %
Gender		
Male	64	58,18 %
Female	46	41,82%
Jumlah	110	100%
Age (Years)		
60 - 64	59	64,9 %
65 - 69	35	38,5 %
70 - 74	12	13,2 %
>75	4	4,4 %
Jumlah	110	100%
Polypharmacy		
2-4	60	54,54%
≥5	50	45,45%
Total	110	100%

Evaluation of Potentially Inappropriate Medications (PIMs) in Outpatient Geriatric Patients at RSKO Jakarta

Table 2. Primary Diagnoses According to ICD-10 Codes at the Drug Dependency Hospital.

ICD-10 Code	Main Diagnosis	Total Main Diagnoses (n=110)	Percentage %
A16	Tuberculosis	1	0,9 %
B18	Hepatitis C	1	0,9 %
B20	Human Immunodeficiency Virus	28	25,4 %
E11	Non Insulin Dependent Diabetes Mellitus	18	16,3 %
E78	Hyperlipidaemia	4	3,64 %
G56	Carpal Tunnel Syndrome	1	0,9 %
G62	Polyneuropathy, Unspecified	2	1,8 %
H10	Conjunctivitis	1	0,9 %
I10	Essential (Primary) Hypertension	26	23,6 %
I11	Hypertensive Heart Disease Without (Congestive) Heart Failure	8	7,2 %
I61	Intracerebral Haemorrhage	1	0,9 %
I64	Stroke, Not Specified As Haemorrhage Or Infarction	3	2,7 %
J02	Acute Pharyngitis	1	0,9 %
J06	Acute Upper Respiratory Infection, Unspecified	2	1,8 %
J10	Influenza With Other Respiratory Manifestations, Influenza Virusidentified	1	0,9 %
K30	Dyspepsia	2	1,8 %
M51	Intervertebral Disc Disorder, Unspecified	1	0,9 %
M54	Sciatica	2	1,8 %
M75	Adhesive Capsulitis Of Shoulder	2	1,8 %
R42	Dizziness And Giddiness	1	0,9 %
R50	Fever, Unspecified	2	1,82 %

Evaluation of Potentially Inappropriate Medications (PIMs) in Outpatient Geriatric Patients at RSKO Jakarta

S42	Fracture Of Shoulder AndUpper Arm	1	0,9 %
Z03	Obervation For Supected Nervous Sstem isorder	1	0,9 %
Total		110	100%

Table 3. Profile of the most common comorbid diseases in geriatric outpatients at the general outpatient clinic and internal medicine department at RSKO Jakarta.

Severity Level	Number of Medical Record Data (n=110)	Percentage %
Mild 1-2 Comorbid	81	73,6 %
Moderate 3-4 Comorbid	9	8,1 %
Severe >5 Comorbid	0	0 %
No Comorbid	20	18,1 %
Total	110	100%

Based on the research findings, it was found that the most visited age group of geriatric patients at the general outpatient clinic and internal medicine department at RSKO Jakarta is the age group of 60 - 64 years. This finding is consistent with a study conducted by Goel et al (2018)¹⁰, which concluded that the geriatric age group between 60 and 64 years tends to exhibit high levels of physical activity and good independence in carrying out daily activities. This directly affects their accessibility to healthcare services, both in clinics and hospitals, to receive outpatient care¹¹. Additionally, their ability to adhere to medication instructions has been proven to be better compared to other geriatric groups, and the age group of 60 to 64 years tends to have a lower number of comorbidities^{10,12}.

The next variable analyzed is gender, where the majority of geriatric outpatient patients at RSKO Jakarta are male. This is due to biological differences in life expectancy between males and females, as emphasized by the World Health Organization (2023), which makes males more vulnerable to age-related diseases and complications. Additionally, lifestyle plays a significant role. Males tend to have riskier lifestyles than females. Smoking, alcohol consumption, and lack of physical activity in males increase the risk of diseases and complications, thus increasing the need for geriatric services. Besides lifestyle factors, social and psychological aspects also have an impact. These research findings are also consistent with the findings of a study by Rumi et al (2023)¹³.

Geriatric outpatients at the general outpatient clinic and internal medicine department at RSKO Jakarta tend to experience polypharmacy, where they receive more than five types of medication. This phenomenon is influenced by several factors, as elucidated by Okuyama (2016)¹⁴.

Pharmacokinetic factors, related to the decline in organ function in geriatrics, such as kidneys and liver, can affect drug metabolism. This can result in a longer half-life of drugs, causing them to stay in the body longer and increasing the risk of side effects. Additionally, a decrease in drug clearance can also lead to drugs not being efficiently eliminated from the body, ultimately increasing the risk of drug accumulation. Pharmacodynamic factors also play a role, as geriatrics tend to have higher sensitivity to drugs. This can increase the risk of side effects even at low doses, as well as the complexity and danger of drug interactions. The presence of comorbidities in geriatrics, who often have multiple chronic diseases simultaneously, is also a factor. This requires treatment with various types of drugs, increasing the likelihood of drug interactions and polypharmacy practices. This is also consistent with the study by Wahyuni et al (2023)¹⁵, which found that the prevalence of polypharmacy prescribing in geriatric patients reached 68.21%.

The study found that geriatric patients at RSKO Jakarta tend to receive polypharmacy prescriptions. The most common primary diagnosis is Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) with the code B.20, as RSKO Jakarta is a One Stop Service hospital for substance abuse (NAPZA)¹⁶. The second most common primary diagnosis is hypertension, followed by type 2 diabetes mellitus. These two diseases also frequently appear as comorbid conditions in geriatric patients. This is due to the susceptibility of the elderly to non-communicable diseases such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and others¹⁵.

Aging causes a decline in organ function, such as the kidneys and heart, which increases the risk of hypertension. Risk factors for hypertension include age, gender, family history, unhealthy lifestyle, and others¹⁴. Aging also increases the

Evaluation of Potentially Inappropriate Medications (PIMs) in Outpatient Geriatric Patients at RSKO Jakarta

risk of type 2 diabetes mellitus through changes in carbohydrate metabolism and unhealthy lifestyle choices. Other contributing factors to the risk of type 2 diabetes mellitus include chronic inflammation, hormonal changes, and the use of certain medications¹⁷. Gastrointestinal (GI)

diseases are also common in geriatric patients at RSKO Jakarta, related to the decline in digestive organ function. Hormonal changes also affect digestive function in the elderly¹⁸.

Incidence Profile of PIMs

Table 4. Frequency profile of PIMs prescribing incidence in geriatric patients at RSKO Jakarta.

Incidence of PIMs	Number of Prescriptions (n=110)	Percentage %
Positif PIMs	59	53,64 %
Negatif PIMs	51	46,36 %
Total	110	100%

Number of PIMs	Number of Prescriptions Identified as Positive for PIMs (n=59)	Percentage %
1 PIMs	41	71,19 %
2 PIMs	16	22,03 %
3 PIMs	2	5,08 %
4 PIMs	2	1,69 %
Total	59	100%

Table 5. Frequency of Top 10 Drug Categories in Prescriptions Identified as Positive for PIMs According to Beers Criteria 2023.

Drug Name	Number of prescriptions Identified as Positive for PIMs (n=59)	Percentage %
Glimepirid	13	16,25 %
Gabapentin	12	15 %
Omeprazole	11	13,75 %
Lansoprazole	11	13,75 %
Acetylsalicylic Acid	11	13,75 %
Sodium Diclofenac	7	8,75 %
Potassium Diclofenac	6	7,5 %
Buscopan Plus (PCT, Hyoscine-N- buthylbromide)	4	5 %
Clonidin	3	3,75 %
Donepezil	2	2,5 %
Total	80	100%

Category PIMs	Number of Prescriptions Identified as Positive for PIMs (n=59)	Percentage %
Avoid	9	11,25 %
Avoid with Caution	71	88,75 %
Total	80	100%

Evaluation of Potentially Inappropriate Medications (PIMs) in Outpatient Geriatric Patients at RSKO Jakarta

Table 6. Classification, Reasons, and Recommendations for Drugs Based on Beers Criteria 2023.

Drug Name	Category in Beers Criteria	Reason	Recommendation
Glimepiride	Avoid with Caution	Can increase cardiovascular risk and hypoglycemia	Avoid unless safer alternatives are available; choose short-acting alternatives if necessary
Gabapentin	Avoid with Caution	Increased risk of severe sedative side effects, including respiratory depression and death	Avoid unless in specific situations such as transitioning from opioid therapy
Omeprazole	Avoid with Caution	Risk of difficult-to-treat infections, pneumonia, gastrointestinal cancer, osteoporosis, and fractures	Avoid use >8 weeks unless for high-risk patients or specific conditions
Lansoprazole	Avoid with Caution	Risk of difficult-to-treat infections, pneumonia, gastrointestinal cancer, osteoporosis, and fractures	Avoid use >8 weeks unless for high-risk patients or specific conditions
Acetylsalicylic Acid	Avoid with Caution	Increased risk of major bleeding due to aspirin in the elderly, without sufficient proven benefit	Avoid using aspirin for primary cardiovascular disease prevention in the elderly
Sodium Diclofenac	Avoid with Caution	Increased risk of gastrointestinal bleeding in patients >75 years or with corticosteroids, anticoagulants, or antiplatelets	Avoid chronic use unless no effective alternatives are available and gastroprotective agents can be used
Potassium Diclofenac	Avoid with Caution	Increased risk of gastrointestinal bleeding in patients >75 years or with corticosteroids, anticoagulants, or antiplatelets	Avoid chronic use unless no effective alternatives are available and gastroprotective agents can be used
Hyoscine-N-butylbromide	Avoid	Highly anticholinergic	Avoid
Clonidine	Avoid	High risk of adverse CNS effects; can cause bradycardia and orthostatic hypotension; not recommended for routine hypertension treatment	Avoid as first-line treatment
Donepezil	Avoid	Causes bradycardia	Avoid

Research at RSKO Jakarta indicates that geriatric patients in general and internal medicine clinics have a significant likelihood of receiving prescriptions for Potentially Inappropriate Medications (PIMs) due to polypharmacy, comorbidities, and organ function decline¹⁹. The incidence rate of PIMs reaches 92.82%²⁰, and 55% of prescriptions for geriatric patients are PIMs²¹. More than 50% of patients receive prescriptions with one category of PIMs based on Beers

Criteria, with the "avoid with caution" category being the most frequently prescribed²¹.

Glimepiride, frequently prescribed in the "avoid with caution" category, has a rapid onset of action and intermediate duration, making it suitable for geriatric patients who need quick and stable glycemic control. Additionally, it has fewer gastrointestinal side effects compared to other sulfonylureas like glipizide²². However, glimepiride is included in the Beers Criteria because its long elimination half-life (10-16 hours)

Evaluation of Potentially Inappropriate Medications (PIMs) in Outpatient Geriatric Patients at RSKO Jakarta

increases the risk of hypoglycemia, especially in geriatric patients with reduced kidney and liver function²³. Side effects such as nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea can exacerbate hypoglycemia and make patients unaware of their condition²⁴. Gundala et al. (2013)²⁵ found that glimepiride significantly increases the risk of severe hypoglycemia in geriatric patients compared to metformin.

Omeprazole and lansoprazole, proton pump inhibitors (PPIs), are categorized as "avoid with caution" because the prevalence of gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) and peptic ulcers increases with age, with about 20-30% of the elderly over 65 years experiencing GERD and 10-15% experiencing peptic ulcers²⁶. Aging reduces saliva production and slows gastric emptying, as well as weakens the lower esophageal sphincter, thus increasing the risk of digestive disorders such as GERD and peptic ulcers²⁷. PPIs are categorized as PIMs based on the Beers Criteria due to the increased risk of enteric infections such as *Clostridium difficile* with long-term use. Additionally, PPIs can disrupt the absorption of vitamin B12, calcium, and magnesium, which are crucial for bone health and nerve function in the elderly²⁸. Long-term use of PPIs is also associated with an increased risk of dementia and cardiovascular disease in the elderly²⁹.

Buscopan Plus, which contains paracetamol and hyoscine n butylbromide (HNB), is often prescribed in the "avoid" category of the Beers Criteria due to the mechanism of action of HNB, which inhibits muscarinic cholinergic receptors in the parasympathetic nervous system. This leads to reduced gland secretion, smooth muscle relaxation, and decreased gastrointestinal motility³⁰. Pharmacokinetically, HNB is readily absorbed after oral administration, reaching peak concentrations within 1-2 hours. Metabolism primarily occurs in the liver, with elimination mainly through the kidneys. Among the geriatric population, HNB has a favorable

pharmacokinetic profile, with a longer half-life and slower elimination process³¹. The inclusion of hyoscine n butylbromide (HNB) in the Beers Criteria is based on its potential for significant side effects in the geriatric population. HNB is known to cause symptoms such as dry mouth, constipation, and dizziness, increasing the risk of falls and injuries in the elderly⁵. Furthermore, the use of HNB can exacerbate underlying medical conditions in the elderly, such as glaucoma, heart disease, and dementia⁵.

Clonidine is known to help reduce the risk of hypertension complications in the geriatric population such as stroke, heart attack, and kidney failure³². Although effective in lowering blood pressure in the elderly³⁰, clonidine is included in the Beers criteria due to its potential significant side effects in this group. Side effects such as hypotension, bradycardia, and fatigue can increase the risk of falls and injuries in the geriatric population⁵. Additionally, clonidine use may not be suitable for geriatric patients with certain medical conditions such as heart disease, stroke, and dementia as it may worsen existing conditions⁵.

Warfarin is also considered a medication that should be avoided and is often prescribed due to its potential interactions with other drugs. This classification is attributed to the proven effectiveness of donepezil in slowing cognitive decline in patients with Alzheimer's and vascular dementia, as well as improving cognitive function, memory, and daily activities in those with mild to moderate Alzheimer's disease³³. However, donepezil is included in the Beers criteria because it can cause bradycardia and hypotension³⁴ and it may interact with anticholinergic and anticonvulsant drugs²⁴. Moreover, research by Birks et al. (2019)³³ indicates that donepezil offers only minimal benefits to patients with mild to moderate Alzheimer's, while Tsuno found that donepezil is not effective in preventing mortality in Alzheimer's patients.

Statistical analysis of the occurrence of PIMs in outpatient prescriptions of geriatric patients at RSKO Jakarta.

Table 7. Chi-Square Test Results: Polypharmacy Status and Incidence of PIMs PIMs.

Number of Drugs	Present		No Present		P-value
	N	%	N	%	
<5	19	17,27 %	40	36,36 %	0.000
>5	40	36,36 %	11	10%	

Table 8. Chi-Square Test Results: Comorbid Status and Incidence of PIMs.

Comorbid Status	Present		No Present		p-value
	N	%	N	%	
Present	57	51,81%	33	30 %	0.000
No Present	2	1,81%	18	16,38%	

Based on the statistical analysis results presented in Table 7 and Table 8, it can be concluded that the p-value <0.05 indicates a significant relationship between polypharmacy status and the occurrence of PIMs, as well as between comorbidity status and the occurrence of PIMs. This demonstrates a significant association between the dependent and independent variables in the context of this study.

Statistical analysis reveals a significant association between the use of more than 5 medications (polypharmacy) and the occurrence of PIMs, as well as between the presence of comorbidities and the incidence of PIMs. These findings indicate that both factors influence the risk of PIMs in patients. The increase in prescribed medications, particularly in geriatric patients with comorbidities, can heighten the risk of PIM

Evaluation of Potentially Inappropriate Medications (PIMs) in Outpatient Geriatric Patients at RSKO Jakarta

occurrence. This is due to the complexity of treatment regimens, heightened potential for drug interactions, and decreased organ function affecting drug metabolism¹⁹. Another contributing factor is that geriatric patients with comorbidities often receive inappropriate prescriptions, duplicate therapies, or incorrect medication dosages, all of which can elevate the risk of PIM occurrence³⁵. These findings align with research conducted by Kumala et al. (2023), which demonstrates a correlation between polypharmacy and the occurrence of PIMs. Both studies show a significance value (P Value) of 0.000, thereby reinforcing the statistical relationship. Furthermore, this research aligns with the findings of Siti Julaiha et al. (2021), who discovered a significant association between comorbidity status and the occurrence of PIMs, with a P value of 0.001.

IV. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study underscore the significance of monitoring Potentially Inappropriate Medications (PIMs) among the geriatric population receiving care at the Drug Dependence Hospital (RSKO) Jakarta. In this research, 3.64% of prescriptions given to geriatric patients at RSKO Jakarta were identified to contain PIMs. Analysis results reveal that among them, PIMs were categorized as avoid in 11.25% and avoid with caution in 88.75%. The study also unveils a correlation between polypharmacy and the occurrence of PIMs in geriatric patients, as well as between comorbid disease status and PIMs occurrence, indicated by a p-value <0.05 through chi-square tests using SPSS software ver. 24. These findings emphasize the necessity for further evaluation by hospitals to enhance awareness regarding prescription compliance, particularly among the geriatric population, aiming to mitigate the risk of PIM occurrence.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Gratitude is extended to God Almighty, to the author's parents, to the faculty members of the Faculty of Pharmacy at Jakarta Global University, to the staff at RSKO Jakarta, and to everyone who contributed to this research.

REFERENCES

- I. Halvorsen K, Kucukcelik S, Garcia B, Svendsen K. Assessing Potentially Inappropriate Medications in Nursing Home Residents by NORGEP-NH Criteria. *Pharmacy*. 2019;7(1):26.
- II. Wulansari A, Wiedyaningsih C, Probosuseno P. Potentially Inappropriate Medication (PIM) pada Pasien Geriatri Rawat Inap di RSUD Dr. H. Moch. Ansari Saleh Banjarmasin. *Maj Farm*. 2023;19(1):91.
- III. Rahmawati R, Harianti Putri Y, Handayani D, Pertiwi R, Putri Nurlita S, Kamilla Putri D, et al. Potensi Penggunaan Obat Tidak Tepat Pada Pasien Rawat Jalan Geriatri Berdasarkan Kriteria Beers 2019 Potentially Inappropriate Medication in Geriatric Outpatients Based on Beers Criteria 2019. *Jurna AKFARINDO*. 2022;7(2):60–5.
- IV. Alhawassi TM, Krass I, Bajorek B, Pont LG. A systematic review of the prevalence and risk factors for adverse drug reactions in the elderly in the acute care setting. *Clin Interv Aging*. 2014;9:2079–86.
- V. By the 2019 American Geriatrics Society Beers Criteria®. American Geriatrics Society 2019 Updated AGS Beers Criteria® for Potentially Inappropriate Medication Use in Older Adults. *Am Geriatr Soc*. 2019.
- VI. Khairunnisa, Ananda MR. Penggunaan Obat Pada Pasien Geriatri Di Instalasi Rawat Jalan Rumah Sakit Universitas Sumatera Utara. *Maj Farm dan Farmakol [Internet]*. 2023;1(6):6–10. Available from: <http://journal.unhas.ac.id/index.php/mff>
- VII. Mahendra E, Tosepu R, Asriati. HUBUNGAN KOMORBID DENGAN KEPARAHAN COVID-19 DI RUMAH SAKIT DARURAT COVID-19 WISMA ATLET KEMAYORAN JAKARTA PUSAT TAHUN 2022 1 Prodi Kesehatan Masyarakat, Pasca Sarjana Universitas Halu Oleo, Kendari, Indonesia 2 Fakultas Kesehatan Masyarakat, U. Ilm Olahraga. 2022;289–300.
- VIII. Wulandari N, Andrajati R, Supardi S. Faktor Risiko Umur Lansia terhadap Kejadian Reaksi Obat yang Tidak Dikehendaki pada Pasien Hipertensi, Diabetes, Dislipidemia di Tiga Puskesmas di Kota Depok. *J Kefarmasian Indones*. 2016;6(1):60–7.
- IX. Qato DM, Wilder J, Schumm LP, Gillet VS, Alexander GC. Changes in Prescription and Over the Counter Medication and Dietary Supplement Use Among Older Adults in the United States, 2005 vs 2011. *JAMA Intern Med*. 2016;176(4):473–82. 2017;176(12):139–48.
- X. Goel V, Rosella LC, Fu L, Alberga A. The Relationship Between Life Satisfaction and Healthcare Utilization: A Longitudinal Study. *Am J Prev Med [Internet]*. 2018;55(2):142–50. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2018.04.004>
- XI. Boulton C, Boulton L, Murphy C, Ebbitt B, Luptak M, Kane RL. A Controlled Trial of Outpatient Geriatric Evaluation and Management. *J Am Geriatr Soc*. 1994;42(5):465–70.
- XII. Curioni C, Silva AC, Damião J, Castro A, Huang M, Barroso T, et al. The Cost-Effectiveness of Homecare Services for Adults and Older Adults: A Systematic Review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2023;20(4).
- XIII. Rumi A, Faisal M, Syarifuddin N, Purwanti R, Natasya P, Serli S. Gambaran penggunaan obat pada pasien geriatri di Puskesmas Dolo Kabupaten Sigi. *J Keperawatan Komunitas*. 2023;12(1):1–11.
- XIV. Okuyama T. Gender differences in pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics. *Drug Metab Dispos*. 2016;44(11):1636–52.

Evaluation of Potentially Inappropriate Medications (PIMs) in Outpatient Geriatric Patients at RSKO Jakarta

- XV. Wahyuni KSPD, Widyaningrum EA, Sari EA, Noerhalizah D. Hubungan Jumlah Peresepan Obat Terhadap Potentially Inappropriate Medications Berdasarkan Beers Criteria 2023 Pasien Diabetes Mellitus. *Indones J Pharm Educ.* 2023;3(2):195–202.
- XVI. AMANDA MP, HUMAEDI S, SANTOSO MB. Penyalahgunaan Narkoba Di Kalangan Remaja (Adolescent Substance Abuse). *Pros Penelit dan Pengabd Kpd Masy.* 2017;4(2):339–45.
- XVII. American Geriatrics Society 2023 updated AGS Beers Criteria® for potentially inappropriate medication use in older adults. 2023;Volume 71(7).
- XVIII. An A, Hadits DAN. Konsep Sistem Pencernaan pada Manusia berdasarkan Al-quran dan Hadits. *J Penelitian, Pendidik dan Pengajaran JPPP.* 2022;3(3):244–51.
- XIX. Misrina T, Intannia D, Lingga HN, Rahmatullah SW. Potentially Inappropriate Medications (PIMs) dan Potentially Prescribing Omissions (PPOs) pada Pasien Geriatri Rawat Inap. *J Pharmascience.* 2023;10(2):296.
- XX. Kumala MT, Suharti T, Prameswari S. Gambaran Penggunaan Obat pada Pasien Geriatri di Puskesmas Dolo Kabupaten Sigi. *J Keperawatan Komunitas.* 2023;12(1):1–11.
- XXI. Hamidah KF, Rahmadi M, Meutia F, Kriswidyatomo P, Rahman FS, Izzah Z, et al. Prevalence and factors associated with potentially inappropriate medication and medication complexity for older adults in the emergency department of a secondary teaching hospital in Indonesia. *Pharm Pract (Granada).* 2022;20(4):1–11.
- XXII. Davidson J. Glimepiride: A Review of Its Use in the Management of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *Drugs Aging.* 2021;38(12):947–56.
- XXIII. Wishart DS, Knox C, Guo AC, Shrivastava S, Hassanali M, Stothard P, et al. DrugBank: a comprehensive resource for in silico drug discovery and exploration. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2006;34(Database issue):668–72.
- XXIV. Qaseem A, Wilt TJ, Kansagara D, Horwitch C, Barry MJ, Forciea MA. Hemoglobin A1c targets for glycemic control with pharmacologic therapy for nonpregnant adults with type 2 diabetes mellitus: A guidance statement update from the American college of physicians. *Ann Intern Med.* 2018;168(8):569–76.
- XXV. Gudala K, Bansal D, Schifano F, Bhansali A. Diabetes mellitus and risk of dementia: A meta-analysis of prospective observational studies. *J Diabetes Investig.* 2013;4(6):640–50.
- XXVI. Katz PO, Dunbar KB, Schnoll-Sussman FH, Greer KB, Yadlapati R, Spechler SJ. ACG Clinical Guideline for the Diagnosis and Management of Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease. Vol. 117, *American Journal of Gastroenterology.* 2022. 27–56 p.
- XXVII. Kanno T, Moayyedi P. Proton Pump Inhibitors in the Elderly, Balancing Risk and Benefit: an Age-Old Problem. *Curr Gastroenterol Rep.* 2019;21(12).
- XXVIII. Kurin M, Fass R. Management of Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease in the Elderly Patient. *Drugs and Aging [Internet].* 2019;36(12):1073–81. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40266-019-00708-2>
- XXIX. Gomm W, Von Holt K, Thomé F, Broich K, Maier W, Fink A, et al. Association of proton pump inhibitors with risk of dementia: A pharmacoepidemiological claims data analysis. *JAMA Neurol.* 2016;73(4):410–6.
- XXX. Chentli F, Azzoug S, Mahgoun S. Diabetes mellitus in elderly. *Indian J Endocrinol Metab.* 2015;19(6):744–52.
- XXXI. Rapid T, Service R, Cadth W. Review of the Clinical Effectiveness and Safety – An Update: Glyburide, Gliclazide or Glimepiride for Elderly Patients with Type 2 Diabetes: A Review of the Clinical Effectiveness and Safety – An Update. 201